

Echoes of the hexagon: the icosikaitetragon (supplemental material)

Paolo Amore

Facultad de Ciencias, CUICBAS, Universidad de Colima,
Bernal Díaz del Castillo 340, Colima, Colima, Mexico
`paolo@uacol.mx`

Mauricio Carrizalez

Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Colima,
Bernal Díaz del Castillo 340, Colima, Colima, Mexico
`mcarrizalez@uacol.mx`

Ulises Zarate

Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Colima,
Bernal Díaz del Castillo 340, Colima, Colima, Mexico
`uzarate@uacol.mx`

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Abstract

We report *all* the curved hexagonal packing (CHP) configurations for $N = 3k(k + 1) + 1$ congruent disks in a regular icosikaitetragon (24 sides) and $k = 2, \dots, 10$.

1 Introduction

We present *all* the curved hexagonal packing (CHP) configurations for $N(k) = 3k(k + 1) + 1$ congruent disks in a regular icosikaitetragon and $k = 2, \dots, 6$ obtained using the *deterministic algorithm* of ref. [1]. k here represents the number of "shells" of a configuration. For a given k we have proved in [1] that the number of nonequivalent configurations obtained with the deterministic algorithm is $\#_{\text{conf}} = k! / \left(\eta n_V \prod_{i=1}^{\ell} n_i! \right)$, where η is a parameter that can take the values 1 or 2 depending if the reflection about an axis passing through a vertex produces a redundant configuration, n_V is the number of vertices of the regular polygon which are occupied by a disk and n_i is the degeneracy of the "building-blocks" of the configuration (for a detailed explanation please refer to [1]).

This document is organized as follows: in [sec.2](#) we present the explicit diagrams for *all* the CHP configurations in the icosikaitetragon up to $k = 6$ shells (notice however that CHPs appear to be optimal only for $k \leq 6$); in [sec. 3](#) we present the Voronoi diagrams for *all* the CHP configurations in the icosikaite-tragon up to $k = 6$ shells.

2 Explicit diagrams

2.1 $k = 1$

Figure 1: CHP configurations for $N = 7$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

2.2 $k = 2$

Figure 2: CHP configurations for $N = 19$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

2.3 $k = 3$

Figure 3: CHP configurations for $N = 37$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

2.4 $k = 4$

Figure 4: CHP configurations for $N = 61$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

2.5 $k = 5$

Figure 5: CHP configurations for $N = 91$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 6: CHP configurations for $N=91$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 7: CHP configurations for $N = 91$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 8: CHP configurations for $N = 91$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

2.6 $k = 6$

Figure 9: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 10: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 11: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 12: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 13: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 14: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 15: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 16: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 17: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 18: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 19: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 20: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

3 Voronoi diagrams

3.1 $k = 1$

Figure 21: CHP configurations for $N = 7$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

3.2 $k = 2$

Figure 22: CHP configurations for $N = 19$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

3.3 $k = 3$

Figure 23: CHP configurations for $N = 37$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

3.4 $k = 4$

Figure 24: CHP configurations for $N = 61$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

3.5 $k = 5$

Figure 25: CHP configurations for $N = 91$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 26: CHP configurations for $N = 91$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 27: CHP configurations for $N = 91$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 28: CHP configurations for $N=91$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

3.6 $k = 6$

Figure 29: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 30: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 31: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 32: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 33: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 34: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 35: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 36: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 37: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 38: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 39: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Figure 40: CHP configurations for $N = 127$ equal circles inside regular polygon of 24 sides.

Acknowledgements

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References

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